

Table 2. Comparison of some physiological traits of Yayou and Shanyou 63. Nanjing, China, 1989.

Trait	Yayou 2	Shanyou 63 (check)	Compared with check ^a
Maximum leaf area index	8.2	7.1	+15.5%
Maximum photosynthetic rate (µmol CO ₂ /m per s)	24.0	20.9	+14.8%*
Specific leaf weight in heading (mg/cm ²)	4.6	3.8	+21.1%*
Chlorophyll content in heading (%)	4.9	4.0	+22.5%*
Relative growth rate (g/kg per d)	40.9	37.8	+8.2%
Net assimilation rate (g/m ² per d)	9.6	6.4	+50.0%
Period leaf activity (d)	73	54	+35.2%*

^a* = significant difference at the 5% level.

area index (LAI) and leaf area duration (LAD) caused a high crop growth rate in the hybrids, leading to the higher average biomass than that of the parents. There was no heterosis in harvest index.

The grain yield potential increased to 11.1-12.5 t/ha, which was much higher than that for the indica or japonica lines. Seed set, however, was low and unstable compared with that of the parents, although the *S-5ⁿ* gene was used. High and stable seed set should therefore be the main objective for cultivating and breeding indica-japonica hybrids.

An example of an indica-japonica hybrid rice is Yayou 2. It was developed by using a chemical hybridizing agent and by crossing indica line 3037 and japonica wide compatibility variety 02428. We compared some of its traits with check Shanyou 63, a widely cultivated indica hybrid.

Yayou 2 showed a grain yield potential of 12 t/ha, 21 t/ha of biomass (1.3% higher than that of the check), and a harvest index

of 0.5, which was 6.4% higher than that of the check. Its LAI increased at a rate of 10.2% per day in the earlier growth stages, which was faster than that of the check, and decreased at 2.0% per day in the later stages, which was slower than that of the check. Its maximum LAI was 1.1 and its LAD 25.5%—both higher than those of the check. Yayou 2 had a leaf photosynthetic rate 14.8% higher than the check and a daily bio-mass accumulation of 17.1% more (Table 2).

The leaves of Yayou 2 were droopy during the early growth stage but later became erect, resulting in a lower light extinction coefficient and a higher light transmission in the later stages. Compared with the check, Yayou 2 had a higher translocation coefficient of stored substances in the sheath, leaf, and stem; a higher relative growth rate and net assimilation rate in the earlier stages; and a longer active period for the three top leaves. ■

assessing variation in chemical composition among cultivars and populations of land races. Scientists have also established an association between electrophoretic components and quality characters in cereals.

Glutelin is the major seed storage protein of rice, contributing 80% of the total endosperm protein. We examined the glutelin banding pattern in 72 japonica and indica rices using the sodium dodecyl sulfate PAGE technique. Three were japonica varieties (Jinbu 4, Vailoninano, and Stagaree E) and 69 were indica varieties, classified as nonscented (23), scented (13), glutinous (9), semiglutinous (9), and deepwater (15).

The different indica varieties showed a similar banding pattern for the major bands. The only exception was the scented variety Kosturi. We observed it to have one mobility variant 6s ($R_f = 0.67$) for band 6, which contributed to a higher molecular weight than the corresponding band in other varieties ($R_f = 0.72$). Differences for some minor bands were noticed among subgroups of indica varieties.

Similarly, variation for glutelin subunits was not found within japonica varieties. However, indica and japonica varieties showed variation for the major band 6. The japonica varieties also had a mobility variant 6s ($R_f = 0.67$) similar to that of Kosturi.

These findings show that glutelin components in rice are conserved, unlike prolamines of wheat and barley. The similarity between indica variety Kosturi and japonica varieties for the slow migrating band 6s indicates the probability of these being distantly related. A detailed study is needed to conclude whether the presence or absence of minor bands in different rice groups has something to do with varietal characteristics. ■

Stress tolerance—drought

Leaf rolling and desiccation tolerance in relation to rooting depth and leaf area in rice

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Greater rooting depth is associated with drought tolerance in a rice variety. However, more water is lost from plants with a higher leaf area. A balance between rooting depth and leaf area is perhaps important. This study was done to understand the relative importance of these two traits in leaf rolling and desiccation tolerance.

Different rooting depths were created by placing perforated polyethylene sheets at 5, 10, and 15 cm in the soil. One treatment with no polyethylene sheet was used as the control. Fertilizer at 20-40-60 kg NPK/ha was applied before IR5 was dry

Grain quality

Glutelin banding pattern in rice assessed

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The high stability of the seed protein profile and its additive nature make seed protein electrophoresis a powerful tool in elucidating the origin and evolution of cultivated plants. The electrophoregram obtained by polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (PAGE) of storage proteins is used mostly for

Water saturation deficit, leaf rolling, and desiccation tolerance of rice as affected by rooting depth and leaf area.^a

Rooting depth (cm)	Leaf area (%)	WSD ^b (%)	Leaf rolling (1-5) ^c	Desiccation ^d tolerance (1-9)	Root zone moisture (%)
5	100	86.0 a	5.0 a	9.0 a	4.0 c
5	50	71.0 b	5.0 a	9.0 a	6.0 c
10	100	50.0 c	5.0 a	8.0 a	6.0 bc
10	50	31.0 d	4.0 a	7.0 a	8.0 ab
15	100	25.0 de	3.0 b	7.0 a	8.0 a
15	50	7.0 f	2.0 e	1.0 c	9.0 a
Control	100	15.0 ef	3.0 b	4.0 b	10.0 a
Control	50	6.0 f	2.0 c	1.0 c	9.0 a
CV (%)		23	11	20	16

^aFigures with the same letter(s) do not differ significantly at the 1% level.

^bWSD (water saturation deficit) (%) = $\frac{\text{Turgid weight} - \text{field weight}}{\text{Turgid weight} - \text{oven-dry weight}} \times 100$.

^cRated on a 1-5 scale where 1 = no leaf rolling and 5 = leaves severely rolled. ^dRated on a 1-9 scale where 1 = no desiccation of leaves and 9 = leaves severely desiccated.

seeded. Seedlings were sprinkled with water for the first 3 wk. The leaf area was clipped to half at 21 d after seeding.

The internal water stress of the leaves was expressed as the water saturation deficit

percentage (WSD%), defined as water deficiency relative to when a leaf was 100% turgid in water. This was measured gravimetrically. The WSD% increased with decrease in rooting depth (see table).

The soil moisture percentage around the root zone decreased as rooting depth decreased. Soil moisture was also reduced with increased leaf area, but only at 5- and 10-cm rooting depths. At 15 cm or deeper, leaf area did not affect the root zone moisture.

Like rooting depth, the leaf area also significantly determines the plant's internal water balance as well as its desiccation tolerance. However, the degrees of leaf rolling and leaf desiccation were significantly reduced with decreased leaf area at 15 cm rooting depth or more. At 5- and 10-cm rooting depths, leaf rolling as well as desiccation tolerance were statistically similar at 100% and 50% leaf area.

Thus, less leaf area is more important at greater rooting depths than at shallower rooting depths when desiccation tolerance of a variety is considered. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Tolerance for Al toxicity in lowland rice

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A major production constraint in acid upland soils is Al toxicity. So far, screening rices for Al tolerance has been limited to upland cultivars. However, lowland rice is grown on about 2 million ha with acid sulfate soil conditions. These rices are prone to Al toxicity during dry spells. Several Al-tolerant upland rices have been identified, but their use in acid lowlands as cultivars or as donors for breeding purposes is very limited because they are japonicas.

Previous investigations showed that relative root length (RRL) of 2-wk-old seedlings (determined as the ratio of root length in a nutrient solution with 30 ppm Al to the root length in a normal nutrient solution) is a good criterion for selecting Al-tolerant genotypes. With the objective of isolating Al-tolerant lowland indicas, we used this technique to screen 62 cultivars originating from acid sulfate soil areas of

India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam, and West Africa.

The experiment, which was laid out in a randomized complete block design with two replications, was conducted in an IRRRI Phytotron glasshouse with 29/21 °C day/night temperatures and 70% relative humidity. IRAT104 was used as the tolerant check and IR1552 as the susceptible check. Eight seedlings were sampled for each test entry in a replication.

The differential tolerance for Al among cultivars was found highly significant (see table). RRL ranged from 0.45 in S-4 to 1.16 in Siyam Kuning. The RRL was 0.83 for tolerant check IRAT104 and 0.57 for susceptible check IR1552. In 17 varieties, RRL was 1.0 or more, indicating that Al did not affect the root growth of these cultivars. Other researchers earlier reported increases in root length and growth of seedlings of tolerant cultivars when exposed to added Al.

The difference in RRL means between tolerant check IRAT104 and the two best performing test varieties (Siyam Kuning and Gudabang Putih) was highly significant. This finding suggests that the tolerance of these two cultivars is very much

Relative root length of some traditional rice varieties grown in normal and Al toxic nutrient solution.

Variety	Origin	Relative root length ^a
Siyam Kuning	Indonesia	1.16
Gudabang Putih	Indonesia	1.14
Siyam	Indonesia	1.10
Lemo	Indonesia	1.09
Khao Daeng	Thailand	1.08
Siyamhalus	Indonesia	1.06
Bjm-12	Indonesia	1.06
Ketan	Indonesia	1.06
Seribu Gantang	Malaysia	1.05
Bayar Raden Rati	Indonesia	1.05
Padi Kanji	Indonesia	1.04
Bjm-13	Indonesia	1.04
Batang Pane	Indonesia	1.04
Bjm-14	Indonesia	1.04
Ca Dung Do	Vietnam	1.04
Bjm-10	Indonesia	1.04
Padi Jambi	Indonesia	1.03
Gablak Cablak	Indonesia	0.96
Barito	Indonesia	0.94
Engatek	Malaysia	0.93
Bjm-15	Indonesia	0.93
Siyam Kuning	Indonesia	0.93
Quisidugo	West Africa	0.93
Lua Thuoc	Vietnam	0.92
Gudabang Kuning	Indonesia	0.92
Bjm-17	Indonesia	0.90
Kutik Putih	Indonesia	0.90
Kapuas	Indonesia	0.89
Baiang 6	Indonesia	0.89
Pontianak	Indonesia	0.85

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